

ISic3059

I.Sicily inscription 3059

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic (pietra di Fuardo)

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lipari

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334783

1. Δ (εκίμου) Ἰουνίου

2. [—].ωνος

3.

4. ΓΑΚ

5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645413

PHI 334783

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 41.0814

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 677

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M. 1991. Meligunìs Lipára V. Scavi nella necropoli greca di Lipari. Rome. At 182 tomba 2179 inv.15382 fig.335

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3059. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388045>